

EVOLUTION AND SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT THEORIES IN JAPAN

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Japan is one of the countries that uses the classic method of catching up in the development of the national economy. It is known that the sustainable growth of the national economy in the catch-up method of development takes place at the expense of the import of technologies. Japan has made great progress in its innovation development at the expense of importing high-tech products produced in the United States, and has raised its export potential to a high level.

Along with the import of modern technologies, Japan began to pay special attention to the development of its own technologies from 1960. In particular, in 1960-1980, the country created an imitation model of economic growth based on its science and technology policy. It should be noted that after the imitation model introduced by Japan in ensuring economic growth, a number of countries in the Asian continent have widely introduced this model in their national economy. The peculiarity of this model was that the country created new ones based on the hybridization of its own technology with the technologies of foreign countries. One of the main achievements of Japan was that such a process was carried out with a well-thought-out plan and purpose.

One of the ways to do this is to buy a lot of patents and licenses from foreign countries, and in order to effectively apply innovative development in the country, it has rapidly established technological parks since the 1950s.

In the 80s of the last century, 18 technopolises were established in 14 cities on the basis of the "Technopolis" program by the Ministry of Foreign Trade and Industry. "Tsukuba" technopolis is the largest among them, occupying an area

of 28,000 square meters and employing 145,000 people. It was the application of new technologies in production that led to Japan's short-term recovery and rapid development in the post-war years. A unique feature of Japan's innovative development is that private business and private companies have discovered new technologies and started attracting scarce financial resources and investments to the economy. Activation of the investment policy developed by private business along with the state made it possible to meet the country's need for financial resources.

In Japan, since the 1980s, new principles and rules of innovative development began to be implemented, the main focus of which was the development of independent research and scientific directions in the country.

Japan's innovation development experience has shown that not only innovations, capital for the discovery of inventions, investment, but also the necessity of innovations for capital and the need for their effective use was also found to be an important factor.

Another aspect of Japan's innovative development experience is the active participation of private business representatives in innovative development. There are two motives behind this, the first is patriotism, and the second is the return of capital invested in innovative activities, its efficiency is much higher than traditional types of activities.

One of the main achievements of the effective development of the innovative economy in Japan is that its main directions have been determined in the country, and all entities that should participate in the process of innovative development, as well as the government, fully fulfill all obligations for the implementation of these directions.

The highest concentration in the Japanese economy is observed in the sphere of providing science and technology development. The Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry performs the task of central administration on

behalf of the state. Such a management system does not exist in the USA and Western European countries, and its main goal is to finance, develop, and implement scientific research that incorporates strategic, long-term, prospective state programs. In Japan, the centralization of ITTKIs and the funding of science for their regulation is carried out by ministries, and large, national laboratories operate on a permanent basis. Also, the development of scientific complexes of centralized large corporations that receive large orders from the state is carried out through the formation of international institutions, programs and projects.

Today, Japan has 23 free import zones, 19 technopolises, and about 300 state and private scientific and technical centers. The biggest difference between Japan's innovation development planning and that of the United States is the existence of a mechanism for determining the effectiveness of ITTKI planning.

The Japanese state has great experience in stimulating innovative activity through taxes, and has been paying attention to this activity since 1952. In Japan, scientific equipment is mainly provided in the form of an accelerated depreciation system, special incentives for the purchase of foreign technologies, and special discounts for research and development expenses. Thanks to a special focus on research and innovation, Japan has become one of the most industrialized countries in the world today. It is not for nothing that Japan ranks 15th in the Global Innovation Index. In order to further accelerate innovative development from Japan, the practice of applying a system of tax, depreciation and other economic benefits to ITTKI entities is widely used. For example, the practice of not taxing the profit obtained as a result of the activities of ITTKI entities, directing that tax base to strengthening their material and technical base, and applying a preferential tariff policy for import operations is widespread.

In most cases, Japan's research and technology application for innovative development is different from that of developed countries. For example, Professor H. Takcheuchi of the Harvard Business School of the USA has shown a number

of aspects of innovative development in Japan. In particular, according to H. Takcheuchi, their main ones are as follows:

- treating the company or firm as a living organism, not as a production subject (machine);

- leaders and managers of companies and firms, that is, responsible employees, organize work based on real reality by relying on their own worldviews, rather than finding some truth and putting it into practice;

- the main focus is not on knowledge and skills, but on the development of the sixth generation of innovative development;

- not the organizational system of enterprises and firms, but the main focus on the self-managing and organizing collective;

- existing disputes are resolved taking into account the opinions and opinions of middle-level employees in the management of the enterprise and firm, this process is considered an important factor in innovative development;

- in-house and outside educational services are widely used to increase knowledge on increasing the efficiency of innovative development.

In addition, the fact that Japan has the lowest level of "brain drain" in the world has a positive effect on the level of innovative development of the country. After all, scientists with scientific potential are the main link of any innovation system. The analysis shows that, according to the World Intellectual Property Organization, Japan ranks first in the world in terms of patents and applications, new trademarks, and industrial designs received by scientists. The table below shows some indicators of innovative activities of national and non-resident economic entities operating in Japan.

Table 1

Some of Japan's largest innovative enterprises¹

<i>N^o</i>	Company name	Fortune Global	Income
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¹ <https://fortune.com/global500/2019/>

		500 ranking	(in million dollars)
1	Toyota Motor	10	272612
2	Mitsubishi	33	145243
3	Honda Motor	34	143303
4	Japan Post Holdings	52	115221

As shown in Table 1, the Fortune Global 500 ranking of the largest companies with the highest revenue in the world is given every year. The main criterion for determining this rating is the amount of income of large companies. A number of Japanese companies are constantly shown in this rating. This, in turn, indicates that the innovative policy and innovative activities in the enterprises have been properly implemented.

In our opinion, one of the unique aspects of Japan's national innovation system is the relatively small share of the state in R&D expenditures, and defense research expenditures are among the lowest among developed countries. Also, due to the economic and technological development of Japanese corporations, more than 80% of ITTKI expenses are carried out at the expense of the private sector. 90% of these corporations are adapted to the production of export-oriented products.

The study of the role of science and innovative technologies in the sustainable development of the Japanese economy served to form the following conclusions:

- Since the 50s of the last century, the Japanese government has introduced new technologies and scientific developments in production as the main criteria for sustainable economic growth. Considering that the economy was in a difficult situation in the post-war period, the government imported new technologies and introduced them into production with further improvement by local scientists. The effectiveness of such practice in the national economy is incomparable, as it is known that the rate of return of the expenses spent on science and

innovative technologies is long-term, which depends on the scientific potential of the nation;

- in economic sources, it is emphasized that Japan's innovative activity has an imitative nature. That is, to this day, Japan is at the top in terms of purchasing patents and licenses from abroad. Most of the goods offered by Japan to the world market are mainly exported in improved, modernized form;
- strong ties are established between large corporations and universities in the country. In this case, the main part of ITTKI expenses of higher education institutions is carried out on the basis of grants from large corporations. For example, Toyota motor, Honda motor, Mitsubishi, Hitachi, Sony, NEC, Toshiba, Fujitsu, Canon, more than 500 multinational companies in the automotive industry, computer technology and other industries are customers of about 100 universities in Japan, such as Tokyo and Kyoto;
- Although Japan's economy has a tendency of steady development in the 20th century, its share in the world market is declining in the next 10 years. According to experts, the occurrence of such a situation is mainly explained by the deepening of the competitive environment in the global market and the entry of new market participants. In particular, the demand for goods offered to the market by China, South Korea, BRICS countries tends to increase.

It should be noted that today Japan's national innovation system is fully formed, and measures are being taken to prevent negative situations occurring in the economy in the following years. For example, the Japanese government has developed a long-term innovative development strategy until 2025 in order to maintain its market share. Based on the "Innovation - 25" strategy, the regulatory and legal base of the national innovation system will be improved. We believe that it is appropriate to apply some aspects of the Japanese national innovation

system in our country. For example, today grants for the development of science are mainly implemented by the state. The signing of scientific and technical agreements between large multinational companies and HEIs in the field of fundamental and applied research will accelerate the work in this regard.

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